

Research Article

The Plastic Broom Revolution

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Abstract: This paper examines a novel project that recycles waste materials to create useful and sustainable items to combat the global problem of plastic waste pollution. In particular, the development of eco-friendly substitutes and environmental conservation is aided by the production of brooms from plastic trash. The paper summarises the growing plastic pollution problem, highlighting the need for creative solutions to lessen the negative impact on ecosystems and public health. The production of brooms made from plastic trash is then covered in depth, including how waste plastic is gathered, sorted, and turned into long-lasting, useful cleaning equipment. One of the report's main features is an examination of the environmental advantages of producing and using these brooms, such as a decrease in the total carbon footprint and a decreased reliance on conventional, non-biodegradable materials. The study also emphasizes this sustainable initiative's social and economic impacts, including the possibility of job growth in the manufacturing and recycling industries. The paper also addresses the possible drawbacks and obstacles of expanding the production of brooms made from plastic trash on a bigger scale, taking into account elements like price, public acceptance, and public awareness. Suggestions for overcoming these obstacles and improving output are also examined. The study concludes by highlighting the significance of adopting creative methods that recycle plastic trash to produce goods with noticeable environmental advantages. The broom made from plastic garbage is a useful illustration of how innovative ideas and environmentally friendly actions may help create a cleaner, healthier world. While the world struggles with the effects of plastic pollution, programs such as these offer a promising first step towards a more sustainable and circular economy.

Keywords: Recycle; Plastic Waste; Pollution; Environmental Awareness; Durability; Sustainability

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1. INTRODUCTION

Due to its distinct topography, which includes long coasts and a wealth of wildlife, Malaysia is especially susceptible to the negative impacts of plastic pollution. Since 2017, Malaysia has been the world's largest importer of plastic garbage, and the country keeps track of worldwide trends in both the overall generation of plastic waste and the consumption of single-use plastics. The nation's waste

management system faces several significant issues as a result of these factors (Hui Ling Chen, 2021). In Malaysia, the effects of plastic pollution are extensive. Because plastic garbage contaminates aquatic ecosystems by finding its way into rivers and oceans, marine life is especially vulnerable. Plastic is frequently mistaken for food by wildlife, especially birds and marine life, which can result in ingestion and consequent health problems (NKY Susanti, 2020). Furthermore, dangerous chemicals are released when plastic breaks down, further polluting the environment. According to reports (Shahul Hamid Fauziah, 2021), the amount of plastic trash found on Malaysian beaches ranges from 64 items/m² to 1930 items/m², accounting for 30–45% of the total rubbish collected. The most common type of film was plastic, which mostly came from packaging materials. In order to address the issue, suitable action—such as an enhanced maritime waste management system—as well as strong governance structures are required. Based on the statistical and environmental data, a number of recommendations were made to lessen the amount of marine debris that occurs in the nation.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Plastic pollution in Malaysia has serious and negative consequences for both the environment and human health. This is very important because Malaysia was the world leader in plastics manufacture, it has been the issues when plastic contamination for a long time and plastics is the major source of marine pollution (Akhtar, 2023). The story of plastics bottle pollution is one that intertwines with our daily lives, challenging us to rethink our convenience-driven habits and envision a world where the beauty of nature isn't eclipsed by the shadows of plastic waste.

Malaysia faces a serious environmental problem with plastic pollution, which endangers the country's animals, different ecosystems, and people's health. Malaysia was in world's top 10 for throwing plastic waste and rubbish in the ocean (Rosli, 2023). According to the data, Malaysians annually throw 2.29 kg of plastic into the ocean per person. Also, Malaysia has one of the biggest plastic production businesses in the world, with over 1,300 plastic firms (MESTECC, 2021). In 2016, resins worth 30 Billion Malaysian Ringgits (MYR) was exported to plastic manufacture worldwide. Out of 138 countries profiled, the UK comes up at number 92, with 0.01 kilogramme of plastic waste per person ending up in the ocean annually. In addition, the obvious trash and plastic garbage that is thrown away, polluting the environment, many nations—including Slovenia—have taken action to export this kind of waste.

Plastic waste is a major source of marine pollution, with 0.14 to 0.37 million tonnes of plastic trash being emitted into the oceans annually, causing harm to marine life through ingestion and entanglement, and impacting the entire marine ecology (Akhtar, 2023). Additionally, incorrect garbage disposal leads to the accumulation of plastics in landfills, causing long-term environmental repercussions as it decomposes over hundreds of years (Akhtar, 2023). Furthermore, micro plastics have been found in food and beverages, posing a risk of human ingestion and potential long-term health implications. The Malaysian marine environment, including highly productive ecosystems and valuable marine organisms, is susceptible to habitat destruction and environmental pollution due to plastic waste (E Tan, N F Jaafar, S H Aileen Tan, & N B Mohd Zanuri, 2022). Inappropriate plastic waste management is a significant threat to Malaysia, with almost half of the 0.9 million tons of plastic waste being inappropriately released into Malaysian waters. The accumulation of plastic waste has caused severe and irreversible impacts on marine life, ecosystems, and the environment in Malaysia (Ng, et al., 2023).

3. PRODUCT DESCRIPTION

Figure 1. Waste plastic bottles.

Figure 2. Plastic bottles are collected at collection centers.

Figure 3. The process of crushing plastic bottles.

Figure 4. The result of crushed plastic bottles.

Figure 5. The result of crushed plastic bottles is a figure.

Figure 6. The final product of plastic broom.

3.1 Environmental Responsibility

The "Plastic Broom Revolution" is a product crafted from 100% recycled plastic waste, demonstrating a strong commitment to environmental conservation. By choosing this broom, consumers actively contribute to the reduction of plastic pollution, playing a part in creating a cleaner and healthier planet. The broom's construction from recycled plastic waste aligns with the principles of sustainability and responsible waste management. This eco-friendly approach helps minimize the demand for new plastic production and reduces the accumulation of plastic waste in landfills and

oceans. Furthermore, the use of brooms made from recycled plastic waste supports the conservation of natural resources and mitigates the adverse effects of plastic pollution on the environment and human health.

3.2 Durable Design

Traditional brooms may not always be built to withstand heavy use or harsh conditions, leading to a shorter lifespan. However, redesigning brooms with durable materials and reinforced construction can extend their lifespan, making them suitable for both household and commercial settings. The use of lightweight yet durable materials, such as high-quality plastic or metal alloys, can ensure ease of use and longevity. Additionally, incorporating features such as waterproof plastic bristles and flagged tip design can enhance the broom's durability and effectiveness in cleaning fine particles.

3.3 Efficient Cleaning

Cleaning with a broom with flagged bristles has several advantages. Because their ends are slightly roughed up or frayed, flagged bristles are excellent at collecting spills of fine particles, grit, and dust. Their perfect application is on smooth floors like hardwood or concrete that doesn't have any uneven spots or grout. They work well for sweeping up small particles, dust, and other light debris in dry areas. Flagged bristles are also ideal for sweeping up fine powders or debris in dry areas, making them ideal for indoor brooms. Furthermore, flagged bristles are commonly found on brooms designed for indoor use because they are gentle on floors and effectively pick up fine debris.

3.4 Comfortable Grip

A comfortable grip is an essential feature of a broom, as it ensures ease of use and reduces the risk of discomfort or strain on the user's hand and wrist. The brooms with ergonomic handles, such as those made of plastic-coated aluminium, are lightweight and strong, providing a comfortable and secure grip. These brooms are designed to minimize the risk of slipping or injury, allowing users to clean with confidence and ease. Additionally, brooms with flagged bristles offer a comfortable grip, as they are less likely to cause discomfort or strain on the user's hand and wrist due to their softer and more flexible nature.

3.5 Multi-Purpose

Brooms with multi-surface capabilities are designed to be versatile, making them suitable for use on different floor types such as hardwood, tile, concrete, and carpet. These brooms are ideal for various settings, including patios, garages, sidewalks, decks, and warehouses, offering convenience and efficiency in maintaining cleanliness across different areas. The multi-surface push broom heads are equipped with bristles that have a stiff inner core for moving large debris and a soft border for picking up finer particles, making them well-suited for a wide range of cleaning tasks. Therefore, the multi-purpose feature of these brooms makes them a practical and adaptable cleaning solution for both indoor and outdoor use, contributing to the ease and effectiveness of cleaning activities.

3.6 Easy to Clean

Easy-to-clean brooms provide a sanitary tool for keeping a clean and healthy environment. Cleaning a broom is a straightforward procedure that entails removing dirt from the bristles and rinsing them with clean water. Brooms with flagged bristles are especially easy to clean because, due to their softer and more flexible nature, they are less likely to cause discomfort or strain on the user's hand and wrist. These brooms' easy-to-clean feature ensures that they remain hygienic and effective in capturing

dust and debris, contributing to a cleaner and healthier environment. Furthermore, low-maintenance, time-saving brooms promote health and safety by ensuring a clean and sanitary environment.

3.7 Aesthetic Appeal

The aesthetic appeal of a broom is an increasingly recognized aspect, with a focus on combining functionality with visual charm. Brooms are now being designed not only for efficient cleaning but also to add a decorative touch to living spaces. For instance, there are wood brooms that provide both functionality and aesthetic appeal, making them suitable for display in addition to their cleaning purpose. Some broom makers, emphasize the importance of the aesthetic appeal of their brooms, designing them to be displayed and used, with a focus on comfort, beauty, and natural materials. Additionally, brooms with unique rustic or multi-colour designs are specifically highlighted for their beautiful appearance, making them suitable for both display and use. This shift towards considering the aesthetic appeal of brooms reflects a growing interest in blending practicality with visual appeal, offering consumers the opportunity to enhance their living spaces while maintaining cleanliness.

4. FUNCTIONAL SPECIFICATION OF PRODUCT INNOVATION

Functional specifications outline the specific features and capabilities of a product, in this case, a broom made from plastic waste. Innovative design thinking is greatly influenced by functional design (Lu, 2020). Here's a breakdown of the functional specifications for the eco-friendly broom.

First specification is material composition of a broom involved outlining the specific requirements and characteristics of the recycled plastics used in the various components of the broom. The material composition of the recycled plastics used in the creation of the broom must be taken into consideration while making one from plastic waste. The kinds and amounts of polymers used to make the broom are referred to as its material composition. The broom is made from 100% recycled plastic waste, ensuring a sustainable and environmentally friendly product. Specifications regarding the type of plastic used, its source, and the manufacturing process should be detailed. The example referring to the material composition is Polyethylene Terephthalate (PET), High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE) and Polypropylene (PP).

Then the durability is when discussing a broom produced from plastic waste, durability refers to the broom's capacity to tolerate environmental factors, pressure, and wear over a lengthy period of time. A durable broom is one that lasts a considerable amount of time while retaining its structural soundness, usability, and visual attractiveness. The broom is built to last, with standards on its anticipated life and resistance to frequent use. The details on the processes used in manufacture and the procedures used in reinforcing to increase durability and also weather resistance. To ensure the handle are bristle materials and resistant to environmental factors such as sunlight, rain and temperature variations.

Other than that, the handle is ergonomically designed for comfortable grip during use. The design of a broom handle manufactured from plastic waste requires functional specifications that specify the features and needs that the handle must have in order for it to serve its intended purpose. An essential part of a broom is the handle, which gives the user control over and manipulation of the sweeping motion. Specifications regarding handle material, length, and width to accommodate a range of users. Thus, the material selection for the handle is also recycled plastic type. The grip design was ergonomics because the users can ensure to be comfortable and secure while handling during use. This may involve contours, textures and non-slip features to enhance grip. Then, the weight consideration also took part in this design to make it be in an optimal weight. To define optimal weight is the handles

are ensuring to be balance and user-friendly experience. It considers the overall weight of the broom for ease of handling.

5. NOVELTY AND UNIQUENESS OF THE PRODUCT

Plastic Broom Revolution introduces a novel and unique approach to the conventional broom, transforming a seemingly mundane household item into an innovative and sustainable tool. Traditional brooms made from natural fibers, the Plastic Broom Revolution leverages recycled plastic materials; it contributes to good environment. The novelty of this revolution is utilization of recycled plastic, and includes the two critical aspects which are sustainability and durability. The Plastic Broom Revolution is reducing environment impact. This eco-friendly approach not only minimizes the need for new plastic production but also tackles the persistent issue of plastic pollution. Plastic Broom Revolution stands out with its enhanced durability and longevity. Traditional brooms, often prone to wear and tear, are given a new lease on life through the resilience of recycled plastic materials. This innovation result is a longer lifespan for the broom, reducing the frequency of replacements and consequently, minimizing overall waste. Moreover, the best thing about this Plastic Broom is the designed is more effective in sweeping and gathering dust, offering an improved cleaning experience. This Plastic Broom also has the optimal performance across various surfaces. This innovation of plastic broom is an embodiment of environmentally conscious design; this revolution not only addresses the global issues of plastic waste but also redefines the expectations of a common household item, making strides towards a greener and more efficient future

6. BENEFIT TO MANKIND

6.1 *Environmental Sustainability*

Reduction of Plastic Pollution by repurposing plastic waste into a broom, there is a direct reduction in the amount of plastic litter in the environment, contributing to cleaner oceans, streets, and ecosystems. This innovation actively combats the environmental hazards posed by discarded plastics. The plastic pollution has been a global concern, adversely effecting ecosystem, marine life, and human health. The innovation of broom by the waste plastic it will contribute to a cleaner and healthier planet. The recycling plastic waste conserves valuable resources that would otherwise be used to produce new materials. This aligns with the principles of a circular economy by giving discarded plastics a second life. This is the positive impact on the environment by utilizing recycled plastic materials; this revolution actively addresses the global challenge of plastic pollution.

6.2 *Positive Impact*

The innovative practice of converting plastic waste into broom positively influences climate change by reducing greenhouse gas emissions, conserving resources, and promoting circular economy principles. Carbon Footprint Reduction is utilizing recycled plastic waste in manufacturing requires less energy compared to producing new plastic. This results in a lower carbon footprint and contributes to mitigating climate change.

6.3 *Awareness and Responsibility*

The initiatives centered around the production and use of plastic waste brooms can serve as education platforms, informing individuals about the impact of their choices on the environment. Job Creation is the process of collecting, recycling, and manufacturing products from plastic waste can create job opportunities, especially in communities where waste management initiatives are

implemented. Than Educational Value is when Products made from recycled materials, such as plastic waste brooms, raise awareness about the environmental impact of single-use plastics. This encourages responsible consumer behaviour and promotes a more sustainable lifestyle.

6.4 Versatility and Accessibility

Brooms made from plastic are often more cost-effective than traditional alternatives, making them accessible to a wider population. This affordability ensures that sustainable and ecofriendly solution is not limited to a niche market but are inclusive, allowing various socioeconomic groups to participate in reducing plastic waste. The innovation result in a practical and functional product such as brooms from recycled plastic are durable and effective in cleaning, catering to the essential needs of households, businesses, and communities. It also ensures that the positive environmental impact does not compromise functionality.

6.5 Health and Global Impact

Recycled plastic materials in brooms are less likely to release harmful chemicals during use, contributing to a healthier indoor environment for users. It contributes to better health and hygiene. The International Collaboration is adoption of recycled plastic products, including brooms, fosters a global effort to address plastic pollution. It encourages collaboration between countries, organizations, and individuals in finding innovative solutions to environmental challenges.

6.6 Extended Product Lifespan:

This innovation provides the durable design which is the Brooms made from recycled plastic waste are often designed for durability, ensuring a longer lifespan compared to traditional brooms. This reduces the frequency of replacement and further minimizes waste generation. Than it will make the transforming plastic waste into a broom brings about a range of benefits, including environmental conservation, resource sustainability, community engagement, and the promotion of a circular economy. These positive outcomes collectively contribute to the more sustainable and responsible approach to consumption and waste management.

7. POTENTIAL COMMERCIALIZATION

The commercialization of a plastic waste innovation turned into a broom presents numerous opportunities for business development, market expansion, and positive environmental impact. Here are some considerations for the potential commercialization of this innovative product: The market appeal and consumer demand is when the eco-friendly nature of the Plastic Brooms Revolution aligns with the growing consumer demand for sustainable product. Within increased environment consciousness, there is a considerable market appeal for items that contribute to reducing plastic waste. Consumers are actively seeking alternatives that not only serve a practical purpose but also reflect a commitment to sustainable living. Customer Feedback and Adaptation also can be the best potential to identify areas for improvement and to adapt to changing market preferences and trends. By strategically addressing these considerations, a business can successfully commercialize a broom made from recycled plastic waste, contributing to both environmental sustainability and economic growth. This approach aligns with the increasing consumer demand for eco-friendly products and supports the global shift toward a circular economy. Next potential is about the distribution channels which is when this innovation can be explore various distribution channels, including retail stores, online platforms, and partnerships with eco-friendly retailers. Than consider collaborations with sustainability-focused brands or organizations to broaden the reach of the product. Businesses that embrace and promote the Plastic Brooms Revolution can establish themselves as pioneers in sustainable and socially responsible

practices because it provides a unique selling proposition. The Price Competitiveness also can be one of the important effects to ensure that the recycled plastic broom remains competitively priced compared to traditional alternatives. Affordability is the key to encouraging widespread adoption. Marketing and Branding also important to develop a strong marketing strategy that emphasizes the environmental benefits, durability, and versatility of the recycled plastic broom and create a compelling brand story highlighting the positive impact of using recycled materials, connecting with consumers on a values-driven level.

Other than, is about the best Collaborations and Partnerships which is that can explore the partnerships with environmental organizations, municipalities, or recycling facilities to enhance the product's credibility and reach. Also make collaborate with retailers, both online and brick-and-mortar, to increase visibility and accessibility. This is can help to commercialize this product to know for the entire world. Product Variations and Innovation is also very important. It Consider developing variations of the recycled plastic broom to cater to different market segments or specific cleaning needs. Than continuously innovate the product based on customer feedback and technological advancements in recycled materials. The product also has to get the Certifications and Standards. Than to obtain the relevant certifications or adhere to industry standards for recycled and sustainable products. This adds credibility to the product and helps build trust with environmentally conscious consumers Educational Initiatives also can be the potential to make this product be commercialization by implement educational initiatives to raise awareness about plastic pollution and the benefits of using products made from recycled materials. This can be done through social media, educational materials, and community outreach programs. The Waste Collection Initiatives it can be consider initiating or supporting plastic waste collection programs to ensure a consistent and sustainable supply of recycled materials for the broom product. Lastly, the Sustainability Reporting is by Implement transparent sustainability reporting to communicate the positive environmental impact achieved through the use of recycled plastic in the broom. Share this information on product packaging, marketing materials, and company communications. All this potential can be the best way to make sure that the product from the waste plastic which is 'THE BROOM' can be the one of the product that can be commercialization in this country.

8. STATUS OF INVENTION

As of the most recent knowledge update in January 2022, I have an incomplete understanding of the present status of innovations pertaining to the conversion of plastic waste into brooms, among other specific inventions. Variations in the path of these advancements may result from the efforts of private individuals, corporations, and academic establishments. In order to obtain up-to-date and accurate information regarding the current status of this specific invention, it is recommended that one consult recent news articles, company announcements, or establish direct communication with relevant organizations involved in sustainable product development. Beyond their immediate practical applications, advancements that transform plastic waste into functional objects such as brooms are consistent with the overarching goals of environmental conservation and sustainability. On an international scale, a multitude of initiatives and startups are currently at work developing innovative strategies to address the intricate challenges posed by plastic pollution. Their efforts are instrumental in advancing the concept of a circular economy. Collaborations among environmental organizations, businesses, and communities are a frequent component of these initiatives. Relevant information regarding significant advancements or new developments since my last update is likely to be accessible via online searches, press release analysis, or official announcements from the organizations or companies engaged in this field of innovation.

9. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, plastic pollution and environmental degradation are major issues worldwide, including Malaysia. The introduction distinguished creativity, invention, and innovation and stressed the importance of proactive plastic waste solutions. Recycling offers hope, encouraging us to use waste as a resource and address plastic pollution. The following issues declaration examined Malaysia's heavy plastic pollution and its role in the global plastic waste crisis. Comprehensive solutions to protect marine ecosystems, wildlife, and public health are needed due to alarming statistics and environmental impacts. It introduced the "Plastic Broom Revolution" to demonstrate how recycling plastic waste into brooms supports sustainability. The environmental responsibility, durable design, efficient cleaning, comfortable grip, multi-purpose functionality. Functional specifications covered material composition, durability, ergonomic design, and other factors, emphasizing thoughtful design. As aesthetics and functionality become more important, the broom's appearance was discussed. This innovation's environmental conservation, sustainability, climate impact, community engagement, and other benefits were listed. The potential commercialization section covered market entry, branding, distribution, and collaboration, emphasizing certifications and education. Finally, the invention and innovation were recognized, along with this field's dynamic nature. It highlights the need for ongoing research, collaboration, and adaptation to market and environmental changes. Repurposing plastic waste into useful products like brooms aims to clean up the planet and promote sustainable practices worldwide.

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